

PLURIDENTITIES

WORKING PAPER 2

Working package 4

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Problem statement

Language and identity are key concepts in the theoretical framework underpinning the Pluridentities project. They are understood as deeply interconnected and dynamically shaped across contexts. Rather than viewing identity as fixed, identification is foregrounded; the ways in which individuals relate to categories such as “multilingual,” “Flemish,” or “European,” and how these relationships shift over time (Cummins, 2015; Janssens, 2019). Language functions not only as a communicative resource but also as a symbolic marker of belonging, linking individuals to groups and cultural communities (J. Li et al., 2022). Within this perspective, plurilingual identities, or pluridentities, emerge through the interaction of linguistic capital, the learning environment, language policy, and technology. Schools therefore constitute central sites in which plurilingual identities can be supported, shaped, or transformed (Cummins, 2000).

Among the components shaping plurilingual identities, linguistic capital plays a central role. It refers to the perceived value of a person’s full linguistic repertoire, including home languages, additional languages, and registers (Bourdieu, 1986; Finegan, 2012). Broad linguistic repertoires can provide social, cultural, and economic opportunities (J. Li et al., 2022; López Blanco, 2025). In school settings, the extent to which linguistic capital is recognised can influence how individuals understand their linguistic resources and how they position themselves within local, national, or broader European communities.

Understanding these processes is particularly relevant in the light of European policy goals that position plurilingual competence as central to lifelong learning and intercultural dialogue (Council Resolution, 2008; Council Recommendation, 2018). Supporting learners’ full repertoires has been shown to strengthen identity building, enhance motivation, and contribute to educational equity (Cummins, 2000; Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2010), while also broadening learners’ horizons and enriching attitudes toward linguistic diversity (Okal, 2014).

One specific pedagogical approach intended to embed multilingualism in classroom practice is Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), in which an additional instruction language is used to teach non-linguistic content. Research suggests that CLIL can support language proficiency, cultural awareness, cognitive engagement, and motivation (Coyle, 2008; Graham et al., 2018; San Isidro Agrelo, 2019; Bulté et al., 2022). Multilingual pedagogies such as translanguaging also enhance metalinguistic awareness and belonging (Cenoz & Gorter, 2015; Lorenzo et al., 2019; Van Raemdonck, 2024). However, the degree to which these approaches are adopted varies significantly across educational contexts.

In Flanders, the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium and the setting of the present study, the historical conflict surrounding the preservation of the Dutch language still reverberates: policymakers today remain highly sceptical of other languages, which they continue to view as a threat to the position of Dutch. As a result, they pursue a strict monolingual policy that exclusively promotes Standard Dutch, leaving little room for multilingualism in education, despite research demonstrating that multilingual education has positive effects (Delarue & De Caluwe, 2015). This context led to strict language legislation, emphasising that only education in the official regional language is permitted. As a result of these sensitivities and fear of Frenchification, the introduction of multilingual education, such as CLIL, only became possible in 2014, 16 years after Wallonia officially started and 10 years after the German part of the country officially started (Mettewie & Van Mensel, 2020; Eurydice, 2024).

Moreover, the introduction of CLIL in Flemish schools is strictly regulated. Only secondary schools are allowed to offer CLIL, and it may cover a maximum of 20% of the curriculum, in German, French, or English. Teachers must have a C1 level in the target language and the necessary CLIL teaching skills. Schools are required to submit a detailed application describing the implementation of CLIL within their educational project. In addition, a parallel Dutch-language program must always be offered, so that participation in CLIL remains a voluntary choice for students, and students must have sufficient proficiency in Dutch to be

allowed to participate in CLIL; their level of Dutch language proficiency needs to be assessed by the class council (Surmont et al, 2023).

Within this strict legislative and historical setting, (CLIL)schools have to realise educational settings in which there is not only attention to language and content learning, but also space for pupils' multilingual identification. Realising such educational contexts require a supportive language policy (LP), as described by Spolsky (2003). According to this model, language policies consist of three components: language management, language practice and underlying beliefs. Considering Flanders' unique historical and sociolinguistic background, it would be very interesting to see to what extent there is a link between CLIL and these three components.

Research questions

This quantitative, survey-based study examines the extent to which participation in a multilingual education model, in this case realised through CLIL, influences individual factors such as (linguistic) identification and more positive perceptions of multilingualism. As such, the study aims to provide insight into the conditions that strengthen inclusive multilingual practices within Flemish education. Based on these objectives and using the Spolsky model as an analytical framework, the following research questions have been formulated.

Theme 1 — Underlying Beliefs

RQ1. Do CLIL and non-CLIL teachers differ in their beliefs about multilingualism and the future relevance of languages?

RQ2. Do CLIL and non-CLIL pupils differ in their beliefs about the perceived importance of languages for their future?

Theme 2 — Language Management

RQ3. Do CLIL and non-CLIL teachers report differently on whether the school language policy permits pupils to use their home language?

Theme 3 — Language Practices

RQ4. Do CLIL pupils exhibit more translanguaging practices than non-CLIL pupils?

Identity

RQ5. Do CLIL and non-CLIL pupils differ in their European, national or regional identity?

RQ6. Do CLIL and non-CLIL teachers differ in their European, national or regional identity?

Hypotheses

Beliefs about multilingualism (RQ1 & RQ2)

H1: It is hypothesised that CLIL teachers actively chose to be part of a multilingual programme and will therefore have a stronger awareness of language. We therefore expect them to have a more positive attitude towards multilingualism and the importance of languages than their non-CLIL counterparts (Lasagabaster, 2017). Given that English is widely considered a global lingua franca and that CLIL in Flanders more often involves English than French (Van Oss et al, 2025), CLIL pupils are expected to perceive English as more important for their future compared to non-CLIL pupils. This reflects both the global instrumental value of English and its greater exposure in the CLIL context (Soler & Morales-Gálvez, 2022).

Language management & practices (RQ3 & RQ4)

H2: Although direct comparative evidence is limited, the available studies suggest that CLIL and non-CLIL teachers may report differently on whether the use of the home language is permitted at school. In CLIL contexts, teachers often indicate that L1 may be used as a strategic support for learning, which is consistent with findings that CLIL teachers consider L1 to be a valuable didactic tool (Lasagabaster et al., 2013). However, the extent to which schools actually take this practice into account has not yet been established.

H3: CLIL learners will exhibit more translanguaging practices than non-CLIL learners. Empirical studies show that translanguaging occurs spontaneously and systematically in CLIL contexts, where learners use different language repertoires to promote understanding and achieve learning goals (Cenoz & Gorter, 2021).

Identification (RQ5 & RQ6)

H4: CLIL participants are expected to be more strongly encouraged to reflect on the social and psychological dimensions of language and culture, thereby deepening their awareness of how language shapes identity. They are therefore expected to identify differently – for example, as more European or multilingual – than non-CLIL participants (Byram, 2012).

Methodology

Dataset

We developed two separate surveys: one addressing teachers and one addressing learners. Each survey was piloted (and adapted where needed) before actual data collection started. Before data collection could start, principals and teachers were asked to give their informed consent. The target group consisted of second and third-grade teachers and pupils aged 14 to 18. For pupils under 16, informed consent was sought from parents in advance, via paper and digital forms. All participants were informed about the purpose and procedure of the study, ensuring anonymity and voluntary participation, following the applicable ethical guidelines. The survey was prepared in Qualtrics and administered between 30 April 2025 and 1 November 2025. It was distributed via a digital link and QR code, which teachers shared with their students or projected in the classroom. For the teacher survey, another link was shared with them. Participants could complete the questionnaire independently and at their own pace, both during class and outside the school context. This approach allowed to reach a broad group of students and teachers easily.

18 schools participated in the study, including 8 CLIL schools, with a total of 215 teachers and 1300 pupils starting the questionnaire. After excluding non-serious responses and incomplete surveys, 127 questionnaires were completed by teachers (12 CLIL teachers and 115 non-CLIL teachers) and 1118 by pupils (162 CLIL pupils, 956 non-CLIL).

Data analysis

In this study, the independent variable is participation in CLIL education. To address theme 1 (underlying beliefs), we examined the differences between CLIL and non-CLIL participants

with regard to their beliefs about multilingualism and the future importance of languages. We operationalised a construct called "Attitudes towards multilingualism at school", which consisted of 10 questions measured using a Likert scale. Based on a factor analysis and using Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.91$) as a test for reliability, items 4, 5, 9 and 10 were removed for the teachers' survey (RQ1) due to insufficient reliability, after which the remaining items were combined into an average score. Group differences were analysed using a t-test. In addition, the future languages were measured using open-ended questions in which pupils could list up to ten languages that they considered important for the future. These were tokenised, standardised and recoded into frequencies per language and per group (CLIL vs non-CLIL) using p-values for each language.

Theme 2 (Language Management) (RQ3) examined how schools' language policies address pupils' home languages. Teachers were asked to indicate how home languages are treated at their school, with the following possible answers: 1 = Prohibited, 2 = Tolerated, 3 = Appreciated, 4 = Actively integrated. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to analyse possible differences between CLIL and non-CLIL teachers.

For theme 3 (language practices) (RQ4), the three items relating to translanguaging among pupils were tested with a factor analysis and for reliability with a Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = .73$) and combined into an average score; group differences were reanalysed using a Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Finally, identity (RQ5–RQ6) was investigated for pupils and teachers by analysing European, national and regional identification. European identity was measured using a scale from 0 (weak) to 10 (strong), where participants could indicate their sense of identification. This question was analysed using a Wilcoxon signed-rank test. All other regions (Europe, Belgium, Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels) were analysed using categorical variables with Fisher's exact tests.

Results

Underlying beliefs

Perceptions towards the importance of pupils' multilingual resources for academic and professional careers were examined among teachers. Six reliable statements were used ($\alpha = 0.77$) and addressed the main language of instruction, general multilingualism, international languages, and minority or regional languages. Responses were given on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = totally disagree to 5 = fully agree). CLIL teachers scored on average similarly to non-CLIL teachers (4.17 vs. 4.20 on a Likert scale), with no significant difference between them (Wilcoxon $p = 0.923$). Variance is relatively limited, indicating that teachers generally have a consistently positive attitude towards multilingualism, regardless of the CLIL profile.

Table 1. Comparison of CLIL and Non-CLIL Teachers on Perceptions towards the importance of pupils' multilingual resources for academic and professional careers

CLIL	N	Mean	SD	Median	p-value (Wilcoxon)
Non-CLIL	103	4.20	0.52	4.33	0.923
CLIL	12	4.17	0.49	4.33	

When we look at the languages that pupils consider important for their future, there is hardly any difference between CLIL and non-CLIL pupils. English, French and Dutch are the most popular choices, followed by Spanish, German and regional Dutch dialects. None of the differences are statistically significant ($p > 0.24$).

Table 2. Languages considered important for pupils' future, by CLIL status

Language	Non-CLIL (%)	CLIL (%)	p-value (Fisher)
English	27%	24%	0.246
French	22%	22%	0.769
Dutch	18%	17%	0.751
Spanish	7%	8%	0.642
German	6%	7%	0.769
regional Dutch dialects	6%	5%	0.918

Language Management

The analysis of language policy at school reveals a significant difference between CLIL and non-CLIL teachers. Respondents were asked how home languages are dealt with at school, with the following possible answers: 1 = Prohibited, 2 = Tolerated, 3 = Appreciated, 4 = Actively integrated. On average, CLIL teachers report a lower level of acceptance of home languages at school compared to non-CLIL teachers (median = 2 versus 1; mean = 1.78 versus 1.25; Wilcoxon $p = 0.014$). This indicates that CLIL schools are more likely to restrict or prohibit home languages, while non-CLIL schools are more likely to tolerate them. The difference, although statistically significant, is relatively small, but suggests a consistent trend in attitudes towards home languages between the two groups.

Table 3. Comparison between CLIL and Non-CLIL teachers reporting on how home languages are dealt with at school

CLIL	N	Mean	SD	Median	p-value (Wilcoxon)
Non-CLIL	100	1.78	0.73	2	0.014
CLIL	12	1.25	0.45	1	

Pupils' language practices

The degree of translinguaging among pupils was measured using three items, combined into an average score. Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.73$) indicates that the items are sufficiently correlated to form a composite score. On average, CLIL and non-CLIL pupils hardly differ in their translinguaging practices (Wilcoxon test: $p = 0.521$). This suggests that both groups use multilingual strategies in the classroom to approximately the same extent. Although there are individual differences within the groups, there is no statistical evidence that CLIL pupils engage in translinguaging more often or more intensively than their non-CLIL counterparts. The results suggest that translinguaging may depend more on personal or contextual factors than on the CLIL programme itself.

Table 4. Comparison between CLIL and non-CLIL pupils in doing translinguaging

Group	N	Mean	SD	Median	p-value (Wilcoxon)
Non-CLIL	889	2.96	1.02	3	0.521
CLIL	153	3.00	0.95	3	

Identity

Among pupils, the analyses show that, on average, CLIL pupils identify slightly more strongly with a European identity than non-CLIL pupils when they rate their identification on a scale of 0 to 10 (8.03 vs. 7.69). This difference was statistically significant according to the Wilcoxon test ($p = .038$). In addition, pupils were asked to indicate which other regions they identify with. Fisher's exact tests showed that CLIL pupils identify significantly more often with Europe, Belgium and Flanders, while no difference was found for Walloon identity. For Brussels identity, the effect was reversed: CLIL pupils chose this option less often.

Table 5. Comparison of CLIL and non-CLIL pupils' identification

Identification	Non-CLIL (%)	CLIL (%)	p_value
European	50%	60%	0.026
Belgian	79%	87%	0.017
Flanders	69%	79%	0.006
Walloon	1%	1%	0.467
Brussels	8%	1%	0.003
None	1%	0%	0.233
Unknown	1%	2%	0.254

A similar analysis was carried out for teachers. CLIL teachers scored higher on average on European identification (8.08 vs. 7.35), but this difference was not statistically significant (Wilcoxon: $p = .179$), presumably due to the small CLIL group and greater dispersion among non-CLIL teachers.

Fisher tests for regional identification also showed no significant differences.

Table 6. Comparison between CLIL and non-CLIL teachers' identification

Identification	Non-CLIL (%)	CLIL (%)	p-value (Fisher)
European	66%	83%	0.334
Belgian	93%	83%	0.213
Flemish	76%	83%	0.731
Walloon	0%	0%	1.000
Brussels	5%	0%	1.000
None	0%	8%	0.189

Conclusions

This study explores how CLIL programmes in Flemish secondary education shape pupils' (linguistic) identification, perceptions of the future importance of multilingualism, language practices among pupils and teachers' approaches to language management. The results paint a nuanced picture in which CLIL is only slightly associated with differences in perceptions and practices, but does show significant connections with pupils' identification.

Regarding underlying teacher beliefs, the results reveal a striking consensus. Both CLIL and non-CLIL teachers attach significant and comparable importance to multilingual resources for pupils' academic and professional futures. The high mean scores and limited variance indicate a broadly held positive attitude toward multilingualism, regardless of the educational profile. The absence of a significant difference suggests that CLIL teachers are not necessarily more outspoken or explicitly pro-multilingual than their colleagues in non-CLIL contexts. This result supports the idea that valuing multilingualism has become a general pedagogical principle within secondary education, rather than a specific characteristic of CLIL education (Pérez-Vidal, 2015).

Among pupils, beliefs about the importance of languages for the future also appear to be largely consistent between CLIL and non-CLIL groups. The dominance of English, French, and Dutch confirms the instrumental nature that pupils attribute to internationally and nationally dominant languages. The fact that no significant differences were found indicates that participation in a CLIL program does not automatically lead to a broader or different hierarchy of languages. In other words, although CLIL focuses on multilingual competence development, this does not necessarily translate into a different perception of which languages are relevant for the future.

A clearer distinction between CLIL and non-CLIL contexts emerges in the domain of language management. The analyses show that CLIL teachers indicate that home languages are, on average, less accepted at school than non-CLIL teachers report. Although the effect is

relatively small, it is statistically significant and consistent. This is striking, as much of the literature suggests that translanguaging is actively encouraged within CLIL, given its benefits for language acquisition and multilingual competences (García & Wei, 2014; Cenoz & Gorter, 2021). However, the finding suggests that CLIL contexts may place a stronger emphasis on target and instructional language consistency, which could lead to a more restrictive policy regarding other languages. Non-CLIL schools appear more tolerant of home languages, which may indicate a more pragmatic or less explicitly regulated language policy.

In contrast, at the level of actual language use by pupils, the results show little difference. Both CLIL and non-CLIL pupils use translanguaging strategies to a similar extent. This suggests that multilingual language use in the classroom is not exclusively or primarily driven by the formal curriculum, but may be more dependent on individual preferences, classroom dynamics, or broader school and home contexts. The absence of a CLIL effect on translanguaging supports the idea that pupils use their multilingual repertoires in a way that is relatively autonomous from institutional frameworks. Our findings differ somewhat from expectations based on the literature, which often assumes CLIL is a positive stimulus for translanguaging (Dalton-Puffer, 2011; García & Wei, 2014).

The most pronounced differences between CLIL and non-CLIL pupils relates to identification. CLIL pupils identify significantly more strongly with a European identification and also more often choose Belgian and Flemish identifications. This finding suggests that CLIL education, which often involves international orientation and exposure to other languages and cultures, is associated with a broader or more layered identification construction. The results suggest that CLIL may primarily align with identities associated with European integration and dominant national or regional frameworks.

A similar, though not significant, trend in European identification was observed among teachers. The lack of statistical significance can plausibly be explained by the smaller CLIL group and the greater dispersion in the non-CLIL group. This finding is in line with the European Commission's (2004) objective of encouraging and promoting multilingualism with

a view to fostering this identification, although no causality between following CLIL and having an EU-identity can be claimed.

When interpreting the results, it is important to take into account some limitations of this study. Firstly, data collection took place during a particularly demanding period for the schools, which reduced their willingness to participate. Mainly, schools and participants with an above-average interest in multilingualism were likely willing to participate. The surveys are based on self-reporting data, for which participants have to assess their perceptions and attitudes, potentially giving rise to social desirability bias. In addition, the length and content-wise complexity of the questions may have been discouraging, causing some participants not to complete the full questionnaire or experiencing reduced motivation towards the end. Moreover, because the survey was self-administered, it is difficult to prevent some students from deliberately filling in incorrect or playful answers, which may undermine the reliability of some data. Finally, the group sizes, particularly among CLIL teachers, are relatively small, which means that some statistical tests may have had insufficient power to detect significant differences.

For future research, it is advisable to use larger and more balanced samples of CLIL and non-CLIL teachers to better identify differences. In addition, observations of classroom practice and qualitative interviews with pupils and teachers could provide more insight into translanguaging and language policy in practice.

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